

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

WP2 – Milestones Achievement Report [Status at M36]

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the results of DataTools4Heart project, especially WP2, towards the achievement of Milestone #4 – A modular Data Ingestion Suite with at least 4 standard based data models tested and validated in 7 European sites.

Milestone #4 was initially due Month 24; we provided a detailed explanation of the work carried out and the latest status in terms of the test and validation of the Data Ingestion Suite in 7 European sites at M24. Thanks to the Project Officer, the deadline has been extended to Month 36 to achieve Milestone #4, and it has been **achieved** with 4 standard-based data models ingested, and the data pipeline validated and test in 7 European sites.

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Acronyms

CDM: Common Data Model

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1 Milestone #4

The milestone is “A modular Data Ingestion Suite with at least four standard based data models tested and validated in 7 European sites” while its means of verification “Data Ingestion Suite has been tested in all pilot sites”. **We achieved this milestone by Month 36 of the project.**

Table 1: Latest status of Data Ingestion Suite for each clinical partner by M36

#	Data Source	Status	Data Model	Data Format	# of developed mappings
1	GEM	Validated	Proprietary	CSV files	10
2	ICRC	Validated	Proprietary	Relational DB	23
3	UCLH	Validated	OMOP	CSV files	14
4	AMC	Validated	Proprietary	Parquet files	15
5	UMCU	Validated	Proprietary	CSV files	11
6	VHIR	Validated	OMOP	Relational DB	13
7	KUH/RS	Validated	Proprietary	CSV files	21
8	BUCH	Validation in progress	Proprietary	Unstructured text files	6*

Table 1 summarises the latest status of the deployment and validation of the Data Ingestion Suite for each clinical partner in the consortium. We have a total of 8 clinical partners, and we validated the Data Ingestion Suite successfully in 7 of them as shown in Table 1. The table also lists the total number toFHIR¹ mappings developed for the ingestion for each clinical partner.

Apart from the data of clinical partners, as technical partners of DataTools4Heart consortium, we agreed to work with MIMIC-IV to test all integrations. We employed the “hosp” module of MIMIC and that enables us to do all the integration activities testing with a real dataset. Even though all clinical partners’ data is ingested and harmonized, having MIMIC as another dataset in the project is an added value for all technical activities. Within the Data Ingestion Suite, we have developed a total of **17** toFHIR mappings² to transform **MIMIC-IV v3.0 hosp** module data to the Common Data Model for Heart Failure Research.

Regarding the standards-based data models, the Data Ingestion Suite can process **5** of them to transform into the Common Data Model for Heart Failure Research:

1. Mapping from OMOP CDM v5.3
2. Mappings from HL7 FHIR R4 & R5
3. Mappings from i2b2³ Data Model
4. SRDC has an open-source tool, called cda2fhir⁴ to transform HL7 Clinical Document Architecture⁵ (CDA) documents to corresponding FHIR resources. Since this is a pluggable

¹ toFHIR, <https://github.com/srdc/tofhir>

² Mappings from MIMIC-IV, <https://github.com/DataTools4Heart/data-ingestion-suite/tree/main/mappings/mimic>

³ i2b2, <https://www.i2b2.org/>

⁴ cda2fhir, <https://github.com/srdc/cda2fhir>

⁵ Clinical Document Architecture, HL7,

https://www.hl7.org/implement/standards/product_brief.cfm?product_id=496

library, once placed into the data pipeline, CDA documents can be transformed to the CDM for heart failure research.

5. Although not a standard like OMOP and FHIR. MIMIC-IV is a widely used research data source in the international research community. We developed the mappings from MIMIC-IV to the CDM and we believe this can be counted as a standards-based model which can have impact to serve MIMIC-IV data through HL7 FHIR conforming to heart failure research profiles, that is the CDM.